

Title: Twin branching in shape memory alloys: A 1D model with energy dissipation effects

Author: Stanisław Stupkiewicz, Seyedshoja Amini, Mohsen Rezaee-Hajidehi

Description: The dataset associated with this publication contains the finite-element codes and the simulation results related to the modeling of twin branching in shape memory alloys.

Methodology: The finite-element codes were developed by using the AceGen system and the simulations are performed in AceFEM, both add-on packages of Mathematica. The postprocessing of the results has been done in Mathematica.

File Formats: Finite-element codes are in .c format. The results, in the form of data plots, are in .csv format.

Size: Few tens of MB

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Access Instructions: The full dataset is available upon request. Contact Mohsen Rezaee Hajidehi (mrezaee@ippt.pan.pl).

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